

ANALYSIS OF THE ZEV GENERATOR WORKPIECE USING SOLIDWORKS SOFTWARE

¹Azizov Sh.M., ²Mallayev Z.S.

^{1,2}Technological machines and equipment, Namangan Institute of Engineering and technology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001025>

Abstract. This article covers the process of analyzing strength, deformation, stress, safety factor, the sequence of algorithms and operations for designing the working part using the Solid works program, and also proposes new carbon-plastic connections, compared to existing connections. Based on the results, conclusions were made and carbon products were proposed.

Keywords: model, calculation, design, shed mechanism, Static design, carbon fiber, solid structures, model, element, force, algorithm, program.

Introduction. Currently, many enterprises use high-performance weaving machines that operate at high speed. As a result, many parts become unusable and wear out slowly. This leads to additional costs and increases the import of spare parts. One of the main units of a weaving machine is the head frame [1].

Analysis of the problem statement. Modern weaving machines operate at a higher speed than the previous ones, due to which the heald frame is quickly replaced by other heald frames. Taking this factor into account, we will analyze heald frames, considering their priority in those made of different materials. For this purpose, we will prepare a working part of a heald frame intended for new high-speed weaving machines[2].

We use the Solid Works CAD program. Since the frames currently used are mainly made of aluminum material, we will start the study with frames made of aluminum material (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Remiz lattice made in Solid Works.

Fig. 2. Remiz material of aluminum

In this case, we first define the fixed parts of the image, which are the edge parts of the part. We fix the part by choosing the method of installing the fastener on two edges. (Figure 3)

Fig. 3. Remiz fixed

After this, we apply a force of 0.05 kg/cm² per 1 cm² with a width of 12 mm and a length of 1800 mm [3]. When calculating, the total force of the base and the tension of the thread are used, which is 12 kg.

Fig. 4. The action of force.

After we have distributed the action of the force on a given surface, in order to determine the limit of the influence of these forces on the remiz, see the stress, determine the shift and deformations. We need to divide the remiz into cells of a certain size in sm². To determine the process of distribution of forces [4], we press the grid button to create a grid.

Fig.4. Creating a grid

After the creation of the network, we press the button "Start tracking" and watch the generated results [5].

Fig. 5. Formation of stress of the part

Fig. 6. Creating a shift

Fig. 7 Deformation in remiz

Research materials and methods.

As can be seen from the above graphs, the frames made of aluminum subjected to intensive movement undergo gradual deformation and displacement. To solve this problem, we propose the following innovation.

We use the autoclave molding method [6]. Wrapping the mold in a package. All the samples are placed in a vacuum autoclave, and then the pressure is changed. Therefore, the solidification technology, which involves the creation of a pressure gradient with respect to atmospheric pressure, is called vacuum bag molding. The main stages of molding:

- 1) The required number of prepreg layers are placed in the mold;
- 2) Using an autoclave, the drying process begins;
- 3) We cut the obtained products according to size.

We wrap the frame with carbon fiber and heat the part wrapped with carbon fiber in the oven at a special temperature by sucking air from the hermetic wrapper in a special cellophane [7]. After our detail is ready in the oven, we will also conduct research in it. In the process of conducting research, we will double the strength, that is, we will reach 24 kg [8].

Fig. 8 Placement of the part in the autoclave

It should be noted that the characteristics of the future product directly depend on the type of vacuum bag, the method of laying it in the mold and other nuances. The obvious advantages and possibilities of the method include:

Molding of large-sized products;
Obtaining the same thickness indicator;
Ideal surface quality;

Fig. 9. Carbon fiber stress forming

Fig. 10. Creating a shift in carbon fiber

Fig. 11 Deformation in remiz in carbon fiber

Fig. 12. The analysis of deformation in carbon fiber considering its yield strength

Conclusion.

As you can see from the diagram and the pictures, the frame treated with carbon fiber will provide several years of efficient operation. As a result, the need for spare parts is reduced. Even if the impact of force increases on the frames treated with carbon fiber, deformation and displacement are not observed.

As can be seen from the stress distribution graph, taking into account the geometric features of our body, the maximum stress is equal to $3.723e^{+0.3}$ (N/meter²) (Fig. 9), the yield limit, i.e. the allowable stress equal to $22.5742e^{+4}$ (N/meter²) takes precedence over the effects of forces and loads on our detail. As can be seen from the displacement distribution graph of the specimens, the maximum displacement modulus value after simulation is $5.514e+0.05$ (meter). Taking into account the geometrical characteristics of carbon remining, the value of the shear modulus allowed for our material is equal to $8.6 e^{+10}$ (mm). As can be seen from the strain distribution graph, the maximum strain value after simulation is $1.415e^{-0.5}$ (Figure 11), so the limit value of carbon material is $4.13613 e^{+9}$ (N meter). Deformation is not observed as a priority in relation to the applied forces and loads.

REFERENCES

1. "Ziyonet.uz", "Exem.uz" "Texnologik dasturlar/uz" va boshqa internet ma'lumotlari.
2. A. A. Сафоев, А. А. Исмаилов, Тармоқ машинасозлиги технологияси, Т., ТТЕСИ, 2007
3. А. А. Сафоев А.О.Obidov "TARMOQ MASHINASOZLIGI TEXNOLOGIYASI". fanidan o'quv-uslubiy majmua Toshkent 2018
4. Shuhrat Azizov, Muhammadaminhon Ibrohimov, Farhod Uzoqov and Mirshoroffiddin Mirzakarimov The modelling and introductions of new type ribs of lattice of the two cylinder of gin E3S Web Conf., 273 (2021) 07020 <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202127307020>
5. Shuhrat Azizov, Muhammadaminhon Ibrohimov, Farhod Uzoqov and Mirshoroffiddin Mirzakarimov. (2022) Statically Analysis of the Stress State of Saw Gins Consisting of 90, 100, 110, 120, 130 Saws. Engineering, 14, 329-338. <https://doi.org/10.4236/eng.2022.148026>
6. Shuhrat Mamatovich Azizov, Xamit Tursunovich Axmedhodjaev. The Optimal Modeling of an Angular Position of Saw Cylinders in Single-Chamber Two Cylinders Gin, American. Journal of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering. Volume 1, Issue 3, November 2016, pp. 103-106. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajmie.20160103.21>
7. Azizov, S. and Axmedhodjaev, H. (2015) Theoretical Analysis of Gin Cylinder for Simulating Dual Saw Cylinder Chamber Gin for Increasing Wear Proof, Energy Efficient, Saving Resources. World Journal of Engineering and echnology, 3, 91-99. doi: 10.4236/wjet.2015.33010
8. Mamamtovich AS (2016) Analysis of the Influence of Geometric Characteristics of the Saw and the Gasket of Saw Gin on the Life of Saw at Different Distances between the Saw. J Textile Sci Eng 6: 256. doi:10.4172/2165- 8064.1000256